

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Begmatova Sokhiba Mustafoevna

LINGUOCULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEXICO-SEMANTIC FIELD

“HAPPINESS” IN THE SYSTEMS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

2023/IYUL

